

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF FLEXURAL AND IMPACT PROPERTIES OF PMMA REINFORCED BY BAMBOO AND RICE HUSK POWDERS

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ABSTRACT

In this research, studying the influence of insert two different types of reinforcing particles, which included: Rice Husk and Bamboo powders which were practical size (25 and 75 μm) and utilize at four various concentrations of (2, 4, 6, and 8 wt.%), to improve in the properties of flexural and impact for heat-cure acrylic resin. The composite specimens of resin and powders were cured at temperature 70-100 °C in a water bath and 2.5 bar for 2 hours. The results showed that the flexural and impact properties became better with low particle size and high concentration. The highest value of flexural strength was (114 Mpa.) for (PMMA- 8% Ba) composite specimens at particles size (25 μm). And the highest value of impact strength was (14.2 KJ/m²) for (PMMA-8%RH) composite specimen at particles size (25 μm).

Keywords: Rice Husk, Bamboo, Flexural, Impact, Heat cure, Weight fraction, Particle Size.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Many biomaterials are ready in fields of medicine and dentistry. Biomaterials can be known as a synthetic or natural material that in attach with body tissues, and classified as metals, polymers, ceramics and composites materials. Polymeric materials have many applications for implantation since they are available in a wide variety of compositions and properties [1-3]. In order to achieve better mechanical strength, it is usually reinforced with natural or synthetic powders or fibers. Natural particles with small size are known to enhance the mechanical properties of polymers [4-6]. The literature surveys include some researches, which are accomplished in this field, it's:

Chow Wen Shyang, (2013), researched the effect of the supplement of hydroxyapatite (HA) particles on the flexural properties of a heat polymerizing PMMA denture base resin. The results illustrated that the flexural modulus, flexural strain and flexural strength of PMMA/HA composites were decreased with the increasing reinforcing (HA) particles [7].

Hanan Abdul et. al, (2013), investigated the influence of the addition natural powder (siwak) on the some properties of PMMA. The results illustrated that any addition of siwak powder lead to reduce in strength of compressive, strength of impact and tensile strength. [8].

Jawad, K. Oleiwi et. al., (2013), researched the influence of the particles size and volume fraction of silica (SiO_2) ceramic particles on the mechanical characteristics of PMMA polymer. The results showed that the maximum shear stress, bending modulus, tensile strength, elongation percentage and modulus elasticity of PMMA composites are increased with increasing the addition of SiO_2 particles and with the increase in the loading filler of SiO_2 particles. Also, the values showed that the impact energy and fracture toughness of PMMA composites decrease with rising in volume fraction SiO_2 particles. Silica particles with small particle size enhanced mechanical properties more than that of large particles size [9].

Mohamed Ashour Ahmed, (2014), investigated the addition of zirconium oxide (ZrO_2) nanopowder with different weight fraction on the some mechanical properties of heat-polymerized acrylic resin. The results showed that significantly increased the fracture toughness, hardness and flexural strength of heat-polymerized acrylic resin, and the best mechanical properties were achieved by adding 7%wt ZrO [10].

Ahmad Bilal et. al., (2014) search the influence of Rice husk (RH) component of the composites and linear medium density polyethylene were applied with maleic anhydride grafted polyethylene (MAPE) on the mechanical properties. They showed that the composites properties (flexural and tensile) get better with a rise in quantity of RH, whereas strength of Charpy impact reduces with rising fiber loading [11].

S.I. Salih et. al., (2015), investigated some properties for PMMA prosthetic complete denture base reinforced by different particles. The results showed that any increase in the concentration of (nHA) and (ZrO_2) particles lead to increases in the flexural properties. The results one recent study showed that the addition of 3% wt of treated titanium oxide nanofiller into PMMA will a highly increases the impact properties, flexural properties, hardness and surface roughness [12].

H. K. Hameed, (2015), investigated the effect of the zirconium oxide (ZrO_2) nano powder to acrylic resin cured by autoclave. The results showed that the addition of silanized Zirconium oxide improved transverse and impact strength of denture base nano composite reinforced with 5% weight fraction of nano- ZrO_2 , also, the results showed slightly increases the surface roughness; hardness and the apparent porosity also decrease by addition of nano ZrO_2 weight fraction increase [13].

Jawad K Oleiwi et. al. (2018), investigated the properties of PMMA when reinforcing with a fiber of Siwak and improvement in the impact properties. The fibers were cut into three lengths and used various concentrations, the results indicated that the impact properties improved with the increasing the fiber length [14].

The aim of this research is to study the flexural and impact properties of heat-cured acrylic resin reinforced by Rice Husk and Bamboo powders for denture applications.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this research, the composite prosthetic complete dentures specimens consist of a polymer matrix and reinforced powders materials. Matrix material included heat curing PMMA that used as fluid resin matrix, type (Spofa Dental Company) to preparation specimens of the composite prosthetic denture base. Two types of natural particles selected with a concentration of (2%, 4%, 6% and 8% wt.) and two particles sizes (25 and 75 μm) it was added to the acrylic powder including (Bamboo and Rice husk) powders. Figure (1) shows the two types of natural materials before and after grinding.

Figure 1 (a) Bamboo Sample after Grinding, (b) Rice Husk Sample after Grinding

The PMMA denture base materials consist of polymer powder and monomer liquid (methyl methacrylate, MMA). The standard proportion in mixing ratio for heat cure acrylic resin is usually volumetric ratio about (2.5) polymer powder (PMMA) and (1) monomer liquid (MMA). When mixing powder and liquid many changes will take place due to the solution of the polymer in the monomer. This ratio was effect on the workability of the mixture, dimensional changes and toxicity of acrylic resin specimens [15]. The mould pressed by using a metallic plate with a size similar to the size of the mould cavity, to obtain a smooth surface and to prevent gases vapor entry into PMMA during the curing. The mixture was covered in closed container with pressure of about 2.5 bars. The curing process of acrylic was performed at conditions of (70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 2.5 bar and 30 min.) according to company instructions.. And then raise temperature for around (30 min.) to the (100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) and stay at this temperature for one hour. Then the process of cooling the mold begins inside the curing device in order to remove the residual monomer.

The flexural test was performed at room temperature by utilizing universal test instrument that same using in the tensile test depended upon three point bending test method. In this method the vertical load was applied gradually at the middle of the composite specimens at strain rate (2 mm/min.) until fracture occurs in it's to obtain the (load displacement) curve for each composite specimen. The flexural modulus and flexural strength are the properties that obtained from this test for each composite specimen was prepared in this study according to the international standard (ASTM D-790) [16-17]. Figure (2) shows the standard flexural test specimen, experimental test machine that was utilized in this study.

Figure 2 (a) Schematic for Standard Flexural Test Specimen, (b) Experimental Flexural Test Specimen before Testing ,(c) Experimental Flexural Test Specimen after Testing ,(d) Flexural Test Machine

The impact test is performed according to international standard (ISO-180) [18] by using Izod Impact test machine type is (XJU series pendulum Izod/Charpy impact testing machine). For Izod Test: the specimen was clamped at one end and held vertically cantilevered beam and it has broken at impact energy of (5.5 J) of pendulum and impact velocity (3.5 m/s) [19]. Impact test specimens might be with or without notch. Figure (3) shows the standard specimen of impact test and Izod impact test instrument that was utilized in this study. The impact results represent the impact strength and the fracture toughness for composite samples that prepared in this study.

Figure 3 (a) Schematic for Standard Impact Test Specimen and (b) Impact test Machine.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure (4) shows the relationship between the flexural strength and weight fraction of the Bamboo powders at both particles size in PMMA resin. The values of flexural strength increased with increasing of the weight fraction for both particles size (25 μm and 75 μm) of Bamboo powders. While figure (5) shows the relationship between the flexural strength and weight fraction of the Rice Husk powders at both particles size in PMMA resin.

Again, the values of flexural strength increased with increasing of the weight fraction for both particles size (25 μm and 75 μm) of Rice Husk powders. The flexural strength of PMMA composite that content Bamboo powders or Rice Husk powder at particles size (25 μm) is higher than flexural strength at particles size (75 μm).

Figure 4 Variation of Flexural Strength with Weight Fraction of Bamboo Powder at both Particles Sizes for PMMA Composite Specimens.

Figure 5 Variation of Flexural Strength with Weight Fraction of Rice Husk Powder at both Particles Sizes for PMMA Composite Specimens.

This is because when the percentage of Bamboo powder reached to the certain value lead to effect on the combination between matrix and powders, results in the strong interface between them and give high flexural strength value of composites. Also, the ability of these powders to prevent the crack propagation inside PMMA matrix according to strengthening

mechanism, in addition to the strong bonding between the PMMA matrix and these powders [20].

Figure (6) shows the dependence of the flexural modulus on the weight fraction of Bamboo powders at both particles size in PMMA resin. The values of flexural modulus increased with increasing of the weight fraction for both particles size (25 μm and 75 μm) of Bamboo powders.

While Figure (7) shows the dependence of the flexural modulus on the weight fraction of Rice Husk powders at both particles size in PMMA resin. The values of flexural modulus increases with increasing of the weight fraction for both particles size (25 μm and 75 μm) of Rice husk powders. The flexural modulus of PMMA composite containing Bamboo powders or Rice Husk powder at particles size (25 μm) is higher than those at particles size (75 μm). This is related to the nature of these natural powders which have high flexural modulus comparing with PMMA, and to the strengthening mechanisms and formation strong bonding between PMMA matrix and these powders [13]. Thus, the flexural modulus values increase from (2.5 GPa.) for PMMA to (3.5 GPa.) for (PMMA - 8% Ba) composite specimen at particles size (25 μm) and to (3.25 GPa.) for (PMMA - 8% RH) composite specimen at particles size (25 μm).

Figure 6 Variation of Flexural Modulus with Weight Fraction of Bamboo Powder at both Particles Sizes for PMMA Composite Specimens.

Figure 7 Variation of Flexural Modulus with Weight Fraction of Rice at both Particles Sizes for PMMA Composite Specimens

Figure (8) displays the change of impact strength with the weight fraction of Bamboo powders at both particles size in PMMA resin. The values of impact strength increased with increasing of the weight fraction for both particles size (25 μm and 75 μm) of Bamboo powders. While Figure (9) shows the dependence of impact strength on the weight fraction of Rice Husk powders at both particles size in PMMA resin. The impact strength values increased with increasing of the weight fraction for both particles size (25 μm and 75 μm) of Rice husk powders.

The impact strength of PMMA composite containing Bamboo powders or Rice Husk powder at particles size (25 μm) was higher than Impact strength at particles size (75 μm). The increase of impact strength behavior may be related to the formation of strong cross-links bonding between the PMMA matrix and these powders which prevent the cracks propagation inside PMMA matrix. Also this is due to the increase of the toughness of the PMMA material. This is because of the addition of natural particles will lead to increase the deformability of the PMMA matrix by release motion PMMA chains. Also attributed to the fact that Bamboo powder and Rice Husk powder are characterized by their higher impact strength than PMMA matrix, therefore that leads to improving the impact strength composite specimens [21, 22]. Thus, the impact strength values increase from (9.3 KJ/m²) for PMMA to (13.2 KJ/m²) for (PMMA - 8% Ba) composite specimen at particles size (25 μm) and to (14.4 KJ/m²) for (PMMA - 8% RH) composite specimen at particles size (25 μm).

Figure 8 Variation of Impact Strength with Weight Fraction of Bamboo Powder at both Particles Sizes for PMMA Composite Specimens.

Figure 9 Variation of Impact Strength with Weight Fraction of Rice Husk Powder at both Particles Sizes For PMMA Composite Specimens.

4. FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

The Figure (10) represents the relationship between fracture toughness and weight fraction of Bamboo powders at both particles size in PMMA resin is shown. The fracture toughness values increased with increasing of the weight fraction for both particles size (25 μm and 75 μm) of Bamboo powders. While figure (11) represents the dependence of fracture toughness on the weight fraction of Rice Husk powders at both particles size in PMMA resin. It can be noticed that the fracture toughness increased with increasing of the weight fraction for both particles size (25 μm and 75 μm) of Rice husk powders.

Again, the fracture toughness of PMMA composite that containing Bamboo powders or Rice Husk powder at particles size (25 μm) is higher than Impact strength at particles size (75 μm). The increase in the fracture toughness is due to the fracture toughness dependence up on the impact strength value and flexural modulus value for each composite specimen. Therefore, when added any type of these particles in the PMMA composite causes a hindering and obstacle the crack propagation inside the PMMA matrix that lead to increasing the impact strength of composite materials.

Figure 10 Variation of Fracture Toughness with Weight Fraction of Bamboo Powder at both Particles Sizes for PMMA Composite Specimens.

Figure 11 Variation of Fracture Toughness with Weight Fraction of Rice Husk Powder at both Particles Sizes for PMMA Composite Specimens.

Also this is due to the nature powders which have high fracture toughness comparing with PMMA [23-26]. Thus, the fracture toughness value increases from (4.822 MPa.m^{1/2}) for PMMA to (6.8 MPa.m^{1/2}) for (PMMA - 8% Ba) composite specimen at particles size (25 µm) and to (6.84 MPa.m^{1/2}) for (PMMA - 8% RH) composite specimen at particles size (25 µm).

5. CONCLUSION

The flexural and impact properties of (PMMA-Ba) composite and (PMMA-RH) composite increased with increasing the fillers loading of (Ba) & (RH) powders. The highest value of flexural strength and flexural modulus were (114 Mpa.) and (3.5 Gpa.) respectively for (PMMA- 8% Ba) composite specimens at particles size (25 µm). The highest value of impact strength and fracture toughness were (14.2 KJ/m²) and (6.9 Mpa.√m) for (PMMA-8%RH) composite specimen at particles size (25 µm).

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